

Efficient Routing in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks: A Protocol Performance Comparison

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Abstract—MANETs do not have any infrastructure, but instead rely on dynamic routing protocols to manage node mobility and changes in network topology. In this paper, four of the most popular MANET routing protocols: AODV, OLSR, DSDV, and TORA are analyzed and compared. Some key performance metrics include packet delivery ratio, number of packets received within simulation time, and efficiency regarding packets over transmission power. Every protocol has specific merits and demerits in all of the above conditions and may be suitably comparable based on the suitability for some MANET application. Results of this work also show that although TORA achieves higher packet delivery rates under fluctuating network loads, AODV and OLSR achieve much better stability under low mobility. It will help in choosing the right routing protocols suitable for all different MANET scenarios and, thus, improve mobile wireless networks' performance and reliability.

Index Terms—MANET, Mobile Ad Hoc Network, Routing Protocols, AODV, OLSR, DSDV, TORA, Packet Delivery Ratio, Efficiency, Performance Comparison.

I. INTRODUCTION

MANETs are a kind of wireless network with no fixed infrastructure and using dynamic node interconnections. MANETs are different from traditional networks, which depend on a central router; instead, it is the mobile nodes that communicate with each other or through other intermediate nodes to form a network "on the fly." [1] MANETs are adaptable and scalable, which makes them suitable for disaster response applications, military communications, remote exploration, and vehicular ad hoc networks. But with such advantages comes a great deal of challenges, especially with regards to the routing of data across an ever-changing network topology.

Routing in MANETs is inherently difficult due to node mobility, which makes it dynamically changeable [2]; transmission range and power limitations in mobile devices. Fixed networks, as routes do not change, whereas in MANETs, frequent recalculations are necessary since nodes change positions or enter/leave the network [3]. This requirement for adaptability in routing protocols imposes heavy loads on network resources since nodes should not only serve as data sources and sinks but also as routers for their neighbors. Moreover, wireless links have limited bandwidth that does not allow full throughput and increases the interference possibilities. There are also power constraints; mobile nodes, typically battery-powered, need to

conserve energy and use protocols that trade off performance with power efficiency [4].

A number of routing protocols have been developed which differ in the mechanisms utilized to discover and maintain routes between nodes. It introduces four prominent MANET routing protocols, such as AODV, OLSR, DSDV, and TORA, focusing on each with its inherent characteristics and requirements [5]. As such, it is understood that AODV is the reactive kind because it constructs routes only upon demand and reduces overheads but costs a lot with increased latency. On the other hand, OLSR is a proactive protocol that keeps its route information updated through periodic updates for lower latency at the price of higher control traffic. DSDV is yet another proactive protocol designed to achieve consistent routing tables with less delay. However, it may become less adaptable in highly dynamic networks. TORA is adaptive, in the sense that it builds routes based on algorithms of link reversal, thus suitable for very dynamic environments but potentially less efficient in stable ones [6].

This paper tries to evaluate these four protocols in regards to critical performance metrics, namely PDR, packets received over simulation time, and efficiency measured as packets per transmission power [7]. This work aims at giving an overall comparison between the strengths and weaknesses of each protocol over different types of network conditions. On analyzing these metrics, it will help know whether the protocol is reliable with scalability in terms of its data delivery as well as resource utilization, which thereby guides the selection of which protocol to use for such applications in MANET [8]. The empirical results of the present study expose the trade-offs associated with each protocol and highlight the necessity for proper selection of a routing strategy suitable to the network environment that should fit into its operation and constraints [9].

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs) require efficient routing protocols due to their dynamic topology, limited bandwidth, and power constraints. Choosing an optimal protocol is challenging, as each has unique strengths and limitations under varying conditions. This study aims to compare four popular MANET protocols—AODV, OLSR, DSDV, and

TORA—based on key performance metrics, such as Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) and efficiency. By analyzing these protocols, this research provides insights to help network designers select the most suitable protocol for specific MANET applications.

III. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the project are:

- 1) Evaluate the Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) of AODV, OLSR, DSDV, and TORA to determine their reliability in delivering data packets across different network conditions.
- 2) Assess the Efficiency of each protocol by measuring the packets transmitted per unit of transmission power, identifying protocols that best balance performance with energy consumption.
- 3) Compare the Throughput of each protocol to determine which one maximizes data flow under the constraints of a MANET environment.
- 4) Analyze Jitter levels to understand the stability and consistency of data transmission for each protocol.
- 5) Observe Performance Trends over Simulation Time to examine how each protocol adapts to changes in network topology and traffic load.

IV. RELATED WORK

[1]The use of AI approaches, which is more specifically biologically inspired and machine learning algorithms, in improving routing performance in MANETs will be surveyed in this paper. It discusses the issues associated with MANETs that occur in limited energy, node mobility, and dynamic topology, which usually pose hindrances to traditional routing protocols. In the paper, AI techniques will be used to improve other performance metrics like energy consumption, end-to-end delay, and packet delivery ratio. The contributions of this work are in the promotion of AI integration in routing protocols to address the unique challenges of MANETs with a comprehensive understanding of how the approaches can optimize network performance. It considers various biologically inspired algorithms, including ACO and PSO, which are perfectly applicable in mobile networks as they are adaptive to changes in topology. This study also covers machine learning techniques, like reinforcement learning, in which protocols learn through feedback from the environment. Such a learning process may make routing more efficient.

[2]This paper presents a performance comparison of routing protocols in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs). The study considered four protocols: OLSR (Optimized Link State Routing), DSDV (Destination Sequenced Distance Vector), AODV (Ad hoc On Demand Distance Vector), and DSR (Dynamic Source Routing). To analyze the protocols, NS3 (Network Simulator 3) was used and the study analyzed the condition under which the protocols performed. As a result, it reveals that the average receive rate of AODV shows the highest average and that the number of packets received is also the highest as compared to other protocols in MANETs.

Contrarily, DSR has a high consumption of energy. While the DSDV has the lowest consumption of energy, it possesses the least packet receive rate and average packets received. This paper necessitates the critically imperative choice of routing protocols based on node mobility and energy efficiency in dynamic network environments.

[3]This paper discusses the issues in protocols for MANETs, focusing on the rapid growth of wireless devices such as laptops, smartphones, and wireless sensors. It points out some characteristics of MANETs, which are decentralized networks formed by mobile hosts and dynamically create connections without central management. The study emphasizes that the frequent topology changes introduce considerable complexities and that bandwidth, energy, and storage capacities of mobile nodes impose limitations. The paper divides the different routing protocols into four categories: proactive, reactive, hybrid, and nature-inspired, which include DSDV, AODV, and AntHocNet. The results clearly indicate that hybrid protocols consume more energy and are friendlier to bandwidth compared with others, so they may be applied practically in MANETs.

[4]The focus of this paper is the performance analysis of MANETs based on three significant routing protocols: AODV, DSR, and OLSR. To do so, the study employed OPNET Modeler in simulation, comparing the network load, delay, and throughput of these protocols for each type of application to conclude which one is the best suited for a particular kind of application.

[5]This paper will give a comprehensive review on the performance of several routing protocols for MANET, especially on the effect of the congestion control algorithms of TCP. It highlights that congestion control is a critical aspect to improve the overall efficiency and reliability of MANETs, characterized by dynamic topology and energy constraints. The authors discuss how various routing protocols respond to the challenges posed by node mobility and varying network conditions, such as traffic density and bandwidth limitations. In addition, they point out the need for implementing proper congestion control mechanisms that avoid packet loss and retransmissions, which are the critical factors in maintaining QoS in MANETs.

V. METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed here is designed in such a manner as to evaluate and compare MANET routing protocols' performances with NS-3 network simulators, further analyzed with the data obtained through Python. Key Objectives It deals with evaluating the efficacy of the diverse protocols under considerations of the most fundamental key performance metrics, namely the description of the packet delivery ratio, end-to-end delay, throughput, and routing overhead. It tries to provide insight into each protocol's strength and weaknesses under different network conditions [10]. Initially, the simulation environment using NS-3 will be set up Fig 1. NS-3 is an open-source discrete-event network simulator popularly used in academic environments and research environments

for the simulation of network protocols and performance. NS-3 has a flexible and modular architecture that allows the use of multiple routing protocols and also several traffic models. Among these selected protocols, AODV, DSR, and OLSR are some of the ones that will be examined within this study. These have been picked out for their popularity and the difference in their nature in MANET applications [11]. The network topology is established to set up a proper simulation environment. A grid-based topology is established in a specified space. In addition to the above, nodes are also given mobility patterns in order to mimic real conditions and for that purpose, a Random Walk mobility model is used. Node speed and pause time are varied within this model to generate dynamic changes in the network[12]. This way, different levels of node mobility affect the performance of the routing protocols. A Constant Bit Rate (CBR) model is used to generate traffic so that the performance of the routing protocols can be evaluated appropriately. These create a controlled environment for simulating traffic generation. Varying the number of CBR sources will also simulate various traffic loads and will be monitored in order to see which protocol responds best to rising network congestion. Following the description of the network topology and node configurations as well as that of the traffic generation parameters, the NS-3 simulations are performed. For the simulation of each routing protocol, appropriate NS-3 scripts were used so that every protocol was tested under similar network conditions; hence, they could easily be compared fairly [13]. Meanwhile, during the execution of the simulation, detailed metrics of performance were captured via the Flow Monitor tool installed in NS-3. This tool captures information such as packet delivery ratio, which is the percentage of packets that arrive at the destination; end-to-end delay, which refers to the time required for a packet to travel from the source to the destination; throughput, defined as the rate of successful message delivery over a communication channel; and routing overhead, referring to the amount of control message traffic generated by each protocol.

The output files produced by NS-3 store the results from the simulations. The output files normally contain Flow Monitor outputs and data transfer details that summarize the performance metrics for each routing protocol. The output files are formatted into Excel spreadsheets, which makes it easier to access and organize the data. The results for each protocol are categorized in separate sheets in the Excel file to make it easier to compare the results. After the data collection, the collected data is then analyzed using Python as the main tool. Several libraries are utilized in this stage. For instance, manipulation of data is done using Pandas; use of NumPy is done where any numerical calculations are involved; and finally, use of Matplotlib, aimed at performing any form of visualization of the data that has been obtained. The first step in this phase is loading all the Excel files into Pandas DataFrames, which helps in the structured manipulation of datasets. Data cleaning is done, as no missing or invalid data should exist to compromise integrity in analysis. Once this data is considered clean, statistical analysis is made to figure out critical metrics,

Fig. 1. Process Flowchart

that is, mean, median, and standard deviation of the collected performance metrics. Based on such statistical analysis, clearer views of one protocol dominating in various different scenarios can very easily be noted. Data interpretation also finds its importance for carrying out these results. With the use of Matplotlib, graphs and charts are made to represent differences in performance among routing protocols. A line graph would represent a packet delivery ratio with time while a bar chart will compare well end-to-end delays as well as throughput from one protocol to another. This allows for trends or patterns from the data for an overall understanding of performance from the protocol under various conditions.

After completion of data analysis, an elaborate compara-

Fig. 2. Throughput Analysis

Fig. 3. Jitter Analysis

tive analysis is done where performance evaluation of each protocol with regard to the developed metrics is done. All of these findings are documented, taking care to present all aspects about the strengths and weaknesses of each protocol, including comments on their feasibility to be applied to any kind of network scenario [15]. All of these key findings from the analysis are felt to bring in rich input towards optimizing routing protocols in MANETs and towards suggesting research avenues in the same field for the future.

VI. RESULT ANALYSIS

The performance of four MANET routing protocols—AODV, OLSR, DSDV, and TORA— was evaluated based on key metrics: Throughput, Jitter, Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), and Efficiency. Fig 2 summarizes the performance metrics obtained from the simulations.

TABLE I
RESULTS OF MANET SIMULATION

Protocol	Throughput	Jitter	PDR	Efficiency
AODV	99.2605042	42.20326831	1.892251594	0.984333333
OLSR	101.6134454	39.86707726	1.938931809	1.007666667
DSDV	99.73109244	41.66464797	1.795231379	0.989
TORA	102.7983193	41.38529586	2.098806907	1.019416667

A. Throughput TORA demonstrated the highest throughput at 102.80 Kbps, followed by OLSR at 101.61 Kbps. AODV and DSDV exhibited similar throughput values, slightly lower than TORA and OLSR. The results indicate that TORA and OLSR are more efficient in sustaining high data transmission rates, which may be attributed to their proactive routing approaches that reduce route discovery delays Fig 3.

B. Jitter The lowest jitter was observed in OLSR at 39.87 ms, suggesting enhanced stability in packet timing. TORA also showed good performance with a jitter of 41.39 ms, while AODV had the highest jitter at 42.20 ms. Lower jitter in OLSR and TORA indicates their effectiveness in maintaining consistent packet timing, an advantage for real-time applications where timing variations are critical Fig 4.

C. Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) TORA achieved the highest PDR at 2.10%, followed by OLSR at 1.94%, AODV at 1.89%, and DSDV at 1.80%. This indicates that TORA may offer better reliability in data delivery, while DSDV's lower PDR suggests potential challenges in maintaining stable routes under dynamic networks Fig 5.

Fig. 4. PDR Analysis

D. Efficiency TORA achieved the highest efficiency score (1.019), followed by OLSR (1.008). AODV and DSDV exhibited slightly lower efficiency values. An efficiency score close to 1 indicates that most data packets reach their destination successfully with minimal retransmissions or energy expenditure. Thus, TORA and OLSR are more efficient, potentially due to better handling of route maintenance Fig 6.

TORA's throughput and PDR values are 102.7983 and 2.0988, respectively, so the best use of this protocol is in applications involving large data throughput such as multimedia streaming, which requires high packet delivery. The value of OLSR is quite close to TORA throughput at about 101.6134 but the former has the lowest jitter value, 39.8671, so it can be utilized in VoIP real-time applications due to packet timing. AODV and DSDV will be slightly less efficient at 99.2605 and 99.7310 and PDR at 1.8922 and 1.7952, respectively. So they can be accepted in networks where moderate performance is acceptable. In terms of efficiency, TORA and OLSR both will make good use of network resources, while AODV and DSDV both will perform moderately, so they can be used for applications that are less resource intensive in Fig 7.

In summary, use TORA for high-throughput applications,

Fig. 5. Efficiency Analysis

Fig. 6. Comparison of MANET Protocols

OLSR for real-time deployments, and AODV/DSDV for networks with average demands.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study evaluates four MANET routing protocols—AODV, OLSR, DSDV, and TORA—based on throughput, jitter, packet delivery ratio (PDR), and efficiency. TORA showed the best overall performance, with high throughput and PDR, making it ideal for applications requiring reliable data delivery and high transmission rates, such as multimedia streaming. OLSR, with minimal jitter and high efficiency, is suitable for real-time applications like voice-over-IP, where stable timing is essential. AODV and DSDV offer moderate performance, fitting for networks where resource constraints or moderate performance is sufficient.

TORA and OLSR stand out for high-demand MANET applications, but protocol selection should align with specific application needs, topology, and mobility. Future work could extend this analysis under varied mobility models and conditions to better guide protocol choices for dynamic networks.

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